

Rugose Spiralling Whitefly – potential threat for agriculture

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Abstract

Rugose spiralling whitefly is an invasive species which entered into India from Central America. It is a polyphagous, Hemipteran insect pest causing a massive threat in many horticultural crops. It produces concentric waxy coating underside of the leaves and produce honeydew which invites sooty mold fungus. Management strategies have been taken to suppress this emerging pest problem in many horticultural crops.

Introduction

Rugose spiralling whitefly (*Aleurodicus rugioperculatus*) is a Hemipteran insect pest which was originally reported from Central America and its distribution was limited within Mexico, Belize, Guatemala infesting Coconut plant during 2004 (Martin, 2004). In India, this whitefly was first recorded in Kerala and later it spread throughout Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Goa and Assam (Sundararaj and Selvaraj, 2017).

Biology of Rugose spiralling whitefly

Adult: Adults are large in size and irregular light brown colour banding appearance in the wings. Males have a pincer like structure at the tip of the abdomen. Adults are sluggish in nature (Stocks and Hodges, 2012).

Eggs: Adult female lays egg in typical concentric waxy spiralling under surface of the leaves and it covers with white waxy matter. Eggs are elliptical in shape and creamy whitish in colour.

Nymph: Nymphs are very small in size (1-1.5 mm length) and golden yellow colour. First instar nymph is known as Crawlers (Mannion, 2010; Stocks and Hodges, 2012).

Host range

It is a polyphagous in nature and confines Coconut, Banana, Mango, Sapota, Guava, Cashew Nut, Maize, Oil Palm, Jack fruit, Bottle Palm, Indian Almond, Oleander (Rao *et al.*, 2018).

Damage symptoms

Adult produces concentric waxy appearance under side of the leaves and both nymphs and adults suck the sap from the leaves by direct feeding especially on underside of the leaflets. Adults produce the large quantities of honey dew excretion which in turn completely darken by sooty mold development on the upper surface of leaves and also understory crops. Formation of sooty mold hamper the photosynthesis process of the plant (Mayer *et al.*, 2010; Stocks and Hodges, 2012).

Management options

The following management strategies should be taken:

1. Installation of yellow sticky trap to attract the white flies.
2. Spraying of Neem oil @ 0.5%
3. Conservation and release of parasitoids like *Encarsia guadeloupae* and *Encarsia dispersa* (Poorani and Thanigairaj, 2017).
4. Besides parasitoids, many predator insect species like *Pseudomallada* sp., *Cybocephalus* sp., *Diadiplosis* sp., *Coccinella septempunctata* can be effectively suppress the whitefly population (Poorani and Thanigairaj, 2017).

Conclusion

It is an exotic insect pest in India and caused huge damage in many horticultural crops including vegetables and ornamental plants. As it has polyphagous nature, it is very difficult to manage this insect pest though different management strategies have been taken globally.

Reference

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